

SHORT NOTES

Quinaldinic Acid Complexes of Vanadium(III)

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When aqueous solution of quinaldinic acid (QH) is added to an aqueous solution of ammonium vanadium alum in slightly acidic medium, an intense blue-violet compound separates. The compound corresponds to the formula, $[V(OH)Q_2] \cdot 3H_2O$. An immediate determination of magnetic moment gives a value of 3.02 B.M., indicating presence of two unpaired electrons, as is expected for a vanadium (III) complex. The compound is stable at room temperature for a couple of hours and then slowly undergoes a change in colour towards pale cream. At about 60° , the water molecules are readily lost with an accompanying colour change to cream. The magnetic moment of the cream-coloured product is found to be 1.7 B.M. and its analytical data are identical with those of oxo-bis-quinaldinato-vanadium(IV), described earlier¹.

We then proceeded to prepare a tris-quinaldinate derivative of vanadium(III). The brown tris-acetylacetonate vanadium (III)², prepared by following Figgis *et al.*³, is dissolved in chloroform and treated with a slight excess of quinaldinic acid in chloroform on a water bath. Pure tris-quinaldinato-vanadium (III) is obtained in the form of red-brown microcrystals. These are stable and give a moment value of 2.66 B.M., indicative of trivalence of vanadium.

The tris-quinaldinato-vanadium (III) in chloroform showed a well-defined absorption maximum at 380 m μ and somewhat flat one at 460-480 m μ . The tris-acetylacetonate-vanadium (III) in chloroform also showed the absorption maximum at 380 m μ . Bielig and Bayer⁴ found that tris-8-hydroxyquinolinato-vanadium (III) in ethanol absorbed at 400 m μ . They observed that tris-8-hydroxyquinolinato-vanadium (III) was quite stable, whereas the compound $[V(OH)(8\text{-hydroxyquinolate})_2]$ is unstable and undergoes rapid oxidation. Our observations on the vanadium (III) quinaldinates appear to be parallel to those of the vanadium (III) 8-hydroxyquinolinates.

Ammonium vanadium alum⁵ was obtained by electrolytic reduction of $(NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot VOSO_4$ solution.

Hydroxo-bis-quinaldinato-vanadium (III) Trihydrate.—Quinaldinic acid (0.6 g) dissolved in boiled water (100 ml), was treated with ammonium vanadium alum (0.5 g in

1. Dutta and Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 1001.

2. Morgan and Moos, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 78.

3. *Ibid.*, 1960, 2480.

4. *Annalen*, 1953, **524**, 96.

5. Palmer, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge Univ. Press, 1934, p. 330.

30 ml boiled water) solution. A blue-violet crystalline precipitate separated, which was filtered, washed successively with cold boiled water, small amount of cold ethanol, and ether. This was then dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 for 30 minutes and was then analysed. {Found: N, 6.24; V, 10.83; H_2O (by loss at 60°), 11.91. $[\text{V}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 6.01; V, 10.93; H_2O , 11.6%}. The compound is insoluble in water, ether, and benzene and is slightly soluble in ethanol. This dissolves in pyridine producing a blue-violet colour which gradually changes on heating to furnish a bluish green product.

The freshly prepared sample was used for determination of magnetic susceptibility in a Curie-type magnetic balance. $\chi_g = 7.532 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 3510 \times 10^{-6}$; diamagnetic correction $= 234 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.02$ B.M. (temp. 30°).

Tris-quinaldinato-vanadium (III).—*Tris-acetylacetonato-vanadium*(III) was obtained as red-brown microcrystals by the interaction of acetylacetonone and ammonium vanadium alum³.

Tris-acetylacetonato-vanadium (III) (1 M), dissolved in chloroform, was treated with a chloroform solution of quinaldinic acid (3 M). The mixed solution was maintained on a warm water bath for 1 hour, chloroform removed, and the red-brown mass was thoroughly washed with ethanol to remove any excess quinaldinic acid. The mass was finally dissolved in chloroform, filtered, and the solution was taken to dryness. *Tris-quinaldinato-vanadium* (III) was obtained in the form of red-brown microcrystals. {Found: N, 7.16; V, 9.10. $[\text{V}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_3]$ requires N, 7.40; V, 9.00% }.

The substance is strongly paramagnetic. $\chi_g = 4.63 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 2624 \times 10^{-6}$; diamagnetic correction $= 275 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.66$ B.M. (30°).

The substance is insoluble in water, slightly soluble in ethanol, and readily so in chloroform or benzene. This is not readily attacked by pyridine.

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